

Phenolic resin/cadmium selenide heterojunctions for efficient hydrogen peroxide production with broad-spectrum light utilization

Zhixiong Zheng^a, Yazhou Zhou^{a,b,c,*}

^a School of Materials Science and Engineering, Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, Jiangsu 212013, China

^b Nanotechnology Centre, Centre for Energy and Environmental Technologies (CEET), VŠB–Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, Ostrava-Poruba 708 00, Czech Republic

^c Max Planck Institute for Polymer Research, Mainz 55128, Germany

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ABSTRACT

The efficient and sustainable production of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) via solar-driven photocatalysis is hindered by poor charge separation and limited light absorption. To address these challenges, we present a novel S-scheme heterojunction photocatalyst composed of cadmium selenide (CdSe) nanoparticles and phenolic resin (RF523). The integration of RF523 with CdSe promotes efficient charge separation by generating a built-in electric field, reducing electron-hole recombination. This design enhances both the oxidation and reduction capabilities of the materials and expands spectral absorption to the near-infrared region (800 nm), which is underutilized in conventional systems. The RF/CdSe-100 composite demonstrated a remarkable H₂O₂ production rate of 888.9 μmol·h⁻¹ under full-spectrum light, outperforming mechanically mixed samples by a factor of 2.0. Additionally, the composite exhibited broad-spectrum light absorption, with an apparent quantum yield of 19.0 % under 365 nm light and 1.7 % under 800 nm light, highlighting its ability to efficiently utilize a wide range of solar energy. The photocatalytic mechanism is driven by the S-scheme charge transfer process, enhancing redox efficiency and promoting the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) for H₂O₂ production. This work offers an efficient strategy for solar-driven H₂O₂ synthesis, advancing the design of photocatalysts for renewable energy and environmental applications.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is a valuable oxidant extensively used in various fields such as oxygen source in the bioremediation, water purification, industrial disinfection, and environmental remediation [1–7]. Current industrial H₂O₂ production relies heavily on the anthraquinone oxidation process, which is both energy-intensive and environmentally taxing [8–10]. Although alternative direct synthesis from hydrogen and oxygen offers theoretical promise, it faces challenges such as high costs, low selectivity, and safety risks. Solar-driven photocatalytic production of H₂O₂ stands out as an emerging technology [11–17]. This approach holds promise, especially for on-site and on-demand H₂O₂ synthesis.

Despite the potential of photocatalysis, challenges remain in achieving efficient H₂O₂ production. Photocatalytic H₂O₂ generation involves complex charge transfer processes where photo-excited electrons and holes must be effectively separated to initiate oxygen reduction and hydrogen oxidation reactions [18,19]. However, photocatalysts

often face limitations like restricted light absorption, rapid electron-hole recombination, and synthesis complexities, all of which hinder performance [20–23]. To address these challenges, advanced material design is crucial, with recent efforts focusing on creating donor-acceptor (D-A) type semiconductive polymers [24]. Their molecular tunability allows precise adjustment of highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) levels. This tunability enables improved charge separation and tailored bandgap structures for enhanced photocatalytic activity. However, such photocatalysts often face issues such as high costs or difficulties in synthesis.

As a low-cost alternative, phenolic resins are attractive for their semiconducting properties, achieved by combining quinone and resorcinol units into π-conjugated D-A pairs [25–28]. However, single-component resins are limited by poor light absorption and high recombination rates. Recent research suggests that heterostructures with tailored internal electric fields (IEF) can alleviate these challenges by accelerating exciton dissociation and charge transport [29–31].

* Corresponding author at: School of Materials Science and Engineering, Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, China.

E-mail addresses: yazhou@mpip-mainz.mpg.de, yazho@ujs.edu.cn (Y. Zhou).

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Fig. 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the preparation of RF/CdSe-X heterojunctions. (b) XRD patterns and (c) FTIR spectra of RF523, CdSe and RF/CdSe samples.

Integrating resins with semiconductors like cadmium selenide nanoparticles (CdSe NPs), which have favorable band alignment and broad light absorption, may offer an effective solution. Previous studies on resins have mainly focused on their roles in adsorption, encapsulation, or as inert supports. In contrast, our work integrates the resin as an active component in a photoactive heterojunction system, forming a built-in interfacial electric field that promotes efficient charge separation and redox reactions. This novel pairing enables the simultaneous enhancement of both the stability and photocatalytic efficiency of CdSe, while also addressing the high recombination rate issue commonly observed in polymeric materials like RF resin.

In this work, we report a novel S-scheme heterojunction system, composed of CdSe nanoparticles and crosslinked polymers RF resin, designed to synergistically enhance photocatalytic H₂O₂ production. Our findings reveal that the RF/CdSe-100 composite exhibited significantly improved photocatalytic activity, achieving an H₂O₂ production rate of 888.9 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under full-spectrum light. This rate was 1.5-, 2.6-, and 2.0-fold higher than those of pure RF, CdSe, and mechanically mixed samples, respectively. This performance underscored the effectiveness of our approach and provided a new strategy for resin-based photocatalysts, highlighting the potential for green H₂O₂ production through solar energy.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Resorcinol, formaldehyde (AR), ammonium hydroxide (AR), acetone, selenium powder (98 %), cadmium chloride (CdCl₂·5H₂O, 98 %), ammonium hydroxide (NH₃·H₂O) and sodium sulfide (Na₂S, 98 %) were obtained from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without further purification.

2.1.1. Synthesis of RF523

The RF resin was synthesized via a hydrothermal reaction. First,

7.2 mmol of resorcinol and 3.6 mmol of formaldehyde were dissolved in 40 mL of deionized water. 3.0 mmol of NH₃·H₂O was then added as a basic catalyst, and the mixture was stirred for 5 min to form a colloidal suspension. This suspension was transferred into a 100 mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and subjected to hydrothermal treatment at 523 K for 24 h. After cooling, the solid product was washed six times with acetone and dried under vacuum at 80 °C for 10 h to obtain a red-orange RF resin powder, referred to sample RF523.

2.1.2. Preparation of CdSe NPs

CdSe NPs were synthesized using a wet-chemistry method. Initially, 1.35 mmol of Se, 5.4 mmol of Na₂SO₃ and 40 mL of deionized water were combined to form Na₂SeSO₃ solution. Then, 0.9 mmol of CdCl₂·5H₂O was added. The resulting mixture was stirred for 2 h, washed three times each with deionized water and anhydrous ethanol, and dried at 60 °C for 12 h to obtain the CdSe NPs.

2.1.3. Preparation of RF523/CdSe composites

RF/CdSe composites were prepared using an electrostatic self-assembly method. A series of samples with varying RF523 contents were prepared by adding an amount of RF523 to a 40 mL aqueous solution containing 206 mg of CdCl₂·5H₂O and 1.468 g of Na₂SeSO₃. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h, then washed three times each with deionized water and anhydrous ethanol and dried at 60 °C for 12 h. The resulting brownish-red powder was named RF/CdSe-X, where X refers to amount of RF523 (i.e., 50, 150, and 200 mg). The control samples were prepared by mechanically mixing CdSe and RF523, denoted as Mix CdSe/RF523.

2.2. Characterization

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) was conducted on a Bruker GADDS diffractometer using Cu K α radiation. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker Vertex 70 spectrometer with KBr powder as the background. Chemical states were analyzed by X-ray

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image of RF523 sample. TEM images of (b) RF523, (c) CdSe, and (d,e) RF/CdSe-100. (f-i) TEM element mapping images of RF/CdSe-100.

photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) on a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha electron spectrometer. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the samples were analyzed by FEI Nova Nano 450. The morphology characterization was conducted on transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and high-resolution TEM (HRTEM). The element distribution was analyzed by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectra (UV-Vis DRS) were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2600 spectrometer with BaSO₄ as a reference. Photoluminescence (PL) measurements were conducted on a fluorescence spectrophotometer with 460 nm excitation. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectra were recorded on a ER200-SRC, A300–10/12 spectrometer.

2.2.1. Evaluation of photocatalytic H₂O₂ production

10 mg of catalyst was added into 50 mL of a 10 % volume fraction isopropanol solution. A 300 W xenon lamp with a full spectrum served as the light source. Prior to irradiation, oxygen was introduced into the system before sealing. During irradiation, 2 mL of the dispersed solution were periodically withdrawn, filtered through a 0.22 μm membrane. H₂O₂ concentrations were analyzed using the iodometric method. Specifically, a potassium iodide (0.4 mol·L⁻¹, 0.5 mL) and potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.1 mol·L⁻¹, 0.5 mL) solution were added to each aliquot. After reacting in the dark for 30 min, absorbance was measured

at 352 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and structural characterization of RF/CdSe heterojunctions

The RF/CdSe composites with CdSe and RF heterojunction were synthesized using a hydrothermal and wet chemical method, as illustrated in Fig. 1a. RF523 resin was first prepared via a hydrothermal reaction using resorcinol and formaldehyde. The synthesized RF523 served as the support material, while CdSe NPs were formed and deposited onto its surface through an electrostatic self-assembly process, resulting in RF/CdSe-X composites with varying resin-to-nanoparticle ratios. XRD patterns of the material confirmed the co-existence of CdSe and RF523 (Fig. 1b), as evident from distinct peaks at 25.4°, 42.0°, and 49.7° corresponding to the (111), (220), and (311) crystal planes of cubic CdSe (JCPDS Card No. 88-2346), along with the peaks of characteristic of RF523 [32]. With increasing RF523 content (i.e., RF/CdSe-150 and RF/CdSe-200), the intensity of CdSe diffraction peaks decreased, suggesting the impact of resin proportion on phase composition, which could impact the electronic properties and interfacial interaction within the composite. FTIR spectra (Fig. 1c) showed the

Fig. 3. Quantitative elemental analysis from the XPS spectra of Cd 3d (a), Se 3d (b), C 1s (c) and O 1s (d) of RF523, CdSe and RF/CdSe-100 samples.

characteristic CdSe peaks at 1220, 1390, and 1580 cm^{-1} , along with prominent RF523 bands [33,34], providing additional evidence of incorporation of CdSe nanoparticles into RF523 to obtain hybrid material.

SEM and TEM images revealed the uniform spherical RF523 particles with the average particle diameter of ~ 320 nm (Fig. 2a, b). As depicted in Fig. 2c, pure CdSe NPs were in aggregation. Fig. 2d and Fig. 2e demonstrated that CdSe NPs as smaller aggregates adhered to the resin surface in RF/CdSe-100. Elemental mapping (Fig. 2f–i) further confirmed the distribution of C, O, Cd, and Se on the composite, confirming the successful synthesis of the RF/CdSe composites. To further confirm the distribution of the CdSe, the SEM and EDS spot analysis for RF/CdSe-100 sample were conducted (Fig. S2). In fact, no Cd or Se element can be observed in the RF523 region based on the EDS maps (Spot 1) while Cd and Se elements can be observed in the composite region (Spot 2). Nevertheless, the CdSe nanoparticles were successfully loaded on the surface of RF523 with an aggregated state in the RF/CdSe-100 sample.

The chemical composition and elemental states of RF/CdSe-100 were analyzed using XPS (Fig. S3). High-resolution Cd 3d spectrum displayed two peaks with binding energies at 404.8 and 411.8 eV, corresponding to Cd 3d_{5/2} and Cd 3d_{3/2}, respectively (Fig. 3a). The peak at 54.0 eV was centered on the Se 3d in the high-resolution Se 3d XPS spectrum (Fig. 3b) [35,36]. Additionally, high-resolution C 1s spectra showed binding energy peaks at 284.80, 286.36, and 290.63 eV, corresponding to C–C, C–O, and C=O bonds (Fig. 3c) [37]. O 1s XPS spectra of RF523 can be fitted with two peaks at 531.32 and 532.71 eV, corresponding to C–O and O–H bonds (Fig. 3d) [38,39]. Notably, the binding energy shifts observed in C 1s and O 1s peaks to lower values, coupled with shifts in Cd 3d and Se 3d peaks to higher values, suggested electron transfer from CdSe to RF523, forming an interfacial electric field (IEF) that promotes directional charge separation. This IEF, directed from CdSe toward RF523, is likely responsible for enhanced charge transfer across the heterojunction, a crucial factor in improving photocatalytic efficiency.

3.2. Photocatalytic performance in H_2O_2 production

The photocatalytic H_2O_2 production performance of RF/CdSe composites with varying ratios was evaluated under full-spectrum light. As shown in Fig. 4a, b, RF/CdSe-100 demonstrated the highest H_2O_2 production rate, reaching 888.9 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, which was significantly higher than those of pure RF523, CdSe, and the mechanically mixed RF/CdSe sample (438.8 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$). When compared with other reported state-of-the-art photocatalysts, the RF/CdSe-100 composite also exhibit a higher catalytic performance (Table S1). This increase in activity was attributed to the intimate interfacial contact between RF523 and CdSe in RF/CdSe-100, which facilitated more efficient electron-proton transport. The impact of varying the resin content was evident, as further increases in RF content in RF/CdSe-150 and RF/CdSe-200 reduced the production rate. This may be due to excessive resin coverage impeding light penetration and reducing active surface area for electron transfer. We further examined the role of different sacrificial agents (isopropanol, n-butylamine, ethanol and methanol) on photocatalytic performance of RF/CdSe-100. Isopropanol emerged as the most effective agent, enhancing H_2O_2 production, whereas n-butylamine yielded negligible H_2O_2 formation, indicating that the nature of the sacrificial agent directly influences the reaction pathway (Fig. 4c, 4d). Importantly, RF/CdSe-100 achieved a respectable H_2O_2 production rate of 435.7 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ in pure water, demonstrating the potential of this catalytic system under ambient, reagent-free conditions, which is advantageous for practical applications. To evaluate the catalytic performance of CdSe and RF523 in the absence of hole scavengers, we conducted photocatalytic H_2O_2 production tests in pure water. As shown in Fig. S4a, b, CdSe and RF523 alone produced 84.9 and 325.4 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of H_2O_2 , respectively, which are significantly lower than the values obtained in the presence of isopropanol. This confirms that isopropanol enhances H_2O_2 production by efficiently scavenging photogenerated holes. CdSe is known to undergo self-oxidation due to photogenerated holes, leading to photocorrosion. This was further confirmed by cycling experiments (Fig. S4c), where a gradual decrease in H_2O_2 production by CdSe was observed over time, dropping to 61 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ after 10 h of light

Fig. 4. (a, b) Photocatalytic performance and H₂O₂ production rates of composite samples with different proportions; (c, d) Performance and H₂O₂ production rate of RF/CdSe-100 under different sacrificial agents. (e) H₂O₂ production performance of RF/CdSe-100 under different light sources; (f) UV visible absorption spectra and AQY of RF/CdSe-100.

irradiation. In contrast, the RF/CdSe-100 composite showed excellent stability: after five cycles, the H₂O₂ production remained at 834.4 μmol·h⁻¹·L⁻¹ in isopropanol and 401.2 μmol·h⁻¹·L⁻¹ in pure water (Fig. S4d,e). These results suggest that the self-oxidation of CdSe is effectively suppressed in the RF/CdSe composite, even when water is used as the electron donor. This enhanced stability and sustained performance strongly support the proposed S-scheme charge transfer mechanism, where photogenerated holes in CdSe are effectively neutralized through interfacial charge migration rather than participating in deleterious self-oxidation.

The impact of different light sources on catalytic performance was also investigated. RF/CdSe-100 was found to be responsive across the full spectrum (Fig. 4e), including the near-infrared region. As shown in Fig. 4f, under monochromatic light at 365 nm, the apparent quantum yield (AQY) reached 19.0%, and the performance continuously decreased with the increase of wavelength. Even under near-infrared light at 800 nm, 1.7% AQY was maintained. This spectral response aligns with the material's UV-Vis diffuse reflectance profile, underscoring the extended photon absorption enabled by the heterojunction.

3.3. Mechanistic Insights into photocatalytic H₂O₂ production on RF/CdSe heterojunction

The superior photocatalytic performance of RF/CdSe-100 was supported by photocurrent response measurements (Fig. 5a), which showed that this composite exhibited the highest photocurrent density among the tested samples, indicative of efficient charge separation. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) results further confirmed these findings, with RF/CdSe-100 exhibiting the smallest Nyquist plot radius (Fig. 5b), indicating reduced interfacial charge transfer resistance. The enhanced contact within the RF/CdSe heterojunction likely facilitated more rapid charge transport. Time-resolved photoluminescence (PL) spectra revealed shorter emission lifetimes for RF/CdSe-100 relative to pure RF523 and CdSe, indicating faster separation of electron-hole pairs (Fig. 5c). Additionally, the ESR spectra taken for 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline-N-oxide (DMPO) in the presence of RF/CdSe-100 exhibit typical signals of DMPO oxidation by ·O₂⁻, confirming the presence of reactive oxygen species that are instrumental in H₂O₂ formation (Fig. 5d) [40, 41]. These results collectively demonstrate that the RF/CdSe

Fig. 5. Sample photocurrent (a) and electrochemical impedance spectra (b) of RF523, CdSe and RF/CdSe-100. (c) Time-resolved PL spectra of RF/CdSe-100 sample excited at 460 nm. (d) EPR spectra of DMPO- $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ of RF/CdSe-100 sample.

heterojunction promotes effective charge separation and enables active generation of reactive species, leading to enhanced photocatalytic activity.

The UV-Vis DRS of RF/CdSe-100 showed a significant extension of the absorption edge, covering a broader spectral range compared to pure CdSe or RF523 alone (Fig. 6a). Tauc plots estimated the bandgaps of RF523 and CdSe are 1.9 and 1.6 eV, respectively (Fig. 6b). Mott-Schottky (M-S) plots for both RF523 and CdSe exhibited positive slopes, confirming their n-type semiconductor characteristics (Fig. 6c). The flat band potential corresponding to the conduction band (CB) level can be determined from the x-axis intercept of the M-S plots. It should be noted that the conduction band of n-type semiconductors was more negative than the flat band potential by 0.1–0.3 V vs. NHE; hence, the E_{CB} values for RF523 and CdSe were determined to be -0.2 and -0.5 eV vs. NHE, respectively. Consequently, the E_{VB} values for RF523 and CdSe samples were 1.7 and 1.1 eV vs. NHE (Fig. 6d). The estimated conduction and valence band positions of RF523 and CdSe suggest a favorable band alignment for an S-scheme charge transfer mechanism.

To further confirm the S-scheme mechanism, in-situ XPS spectra of the RF/CdSe-100 sample were tested under light irradiation. Compared with the C 1 s, O 1 s, Cd 3d and Se 3d pattern prior to light exposure, positive shifts in binding energies: peaks for C 1 s (~ 0.12 eV) and O 1 s (1.67 eV) were observed, while Cd 3d (~ 0.21 eV) and Se 3d (0.15 eV) shifted negatively under illumination (Fig. 7). This indicates a backflow of photogenerated electrons from RF523 to CdSe, consistent with an S-scheme mechanism. In this arrangement, electrons in RF523's conduction band recombine with holes in valence band of CdSe, facilitating spatial separation of electrons and holes at opposite ends of the heterojunction, which enhances overall redox capability and stability under light.

Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) at various rotation speeds (Fig. 8a) provided insights into the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) pathway and H_2O_2 generation of the RF/CdSe-100 photocatalyst. As the rotation

speed increased, the cathodic current density rose, reflecting the impact of diffusion-layer control on electron transfer rates. The Koutecky-Levich (K-L) plot derived from these results exhibited good linearity, with an estimated electron-transfer number (n) of approximately 1.82 (Fig. 8b), indicating that RF/CdSe-100 primarily follows a two-electron pathway for ORR, yielding H_2O_2 as the main product (Fig. 8c) [42].

A schematic diagram of the proposed photocatalytic mechanism is shown in Fig. 9. Under light excitation, electrons in the valence band of RF523 are excited to its conduction band and, under the influence of the interfacial electric field, migrate towards CdSe. These electrons then participate in ORR on the CdSe surface, generating $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ radicals, which subsequently lead to H_2O_2 formation. The internal electric field within the heterojunction directs this electron flow and spatially separates electrons and holes, effectively reducing recombination and enhancing photocatalytic efficiency.

4. Conclusions

In summary, we have successfully synthesized a novel RF/CdSe S-scheme heterojunction composites for enhanced photocatalytic H_2O_2 production under full-spectrum light. These materials contained a well-defined interfacial electric field, which significantly improved the separation of photogenerated charge carriers and facilitated efficient charge transfer. This heterojunction structure not only broadens the material's light absorption spectrum but also enhanced the photocatalytic H_2O_2 production rate, achieving an optimal production rate of $888.9 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under full light irradiation. This is 1.5, 2.6, and 2.0 times higher than that of pure RF, CdSe, and the mechanically mixed samples, respectively. Furthermore, the material demonstrated a high AQY of 19.0 % under 365 nm light and maintained 1.7 % AQY even under near-infrared (NIR) light (800 nm), further confirming the broad light absorption range of the composite. The photocatalytic mechanism was thoroughly investigated, revealing an S-scheme charge transfer pathway

Fig. 6. (a) UV Vis DRS spectra of RF523, CdSe and RF/CdSe-100; (b) Tauc diagrams and optical bandgaps of RF523 and CdSe. (c) M-S curves of RF523 and CdSe; (d) The electronic band structures of RF523 and CdSe.

Fig. 7. The high-resolution analysis from the XPS spectra of C 1s (a), O 1s (b), Cd 3d (c) and Se 3d (d) in dark and light conditions.

Fig. 8. (a) Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) of RF/CdSe-100 at different rotating speeds ranging from 900 to 2025 rpm. (b) K-L curves of RF/CdSe-100 corresponding average electron transfer numbers. (c) The two-step one-electron route for H₂O₂ photoproduction.

Fig. 9. Schematic diagram of RF/CdSe-100 photocatalytic charge transfer and mechanism.

that maximizes charge separation and reduces recombination, enabling efficient H₂O₂ production. This work offers a new approach for designing efficient, low-cost photocatalysts based on polymeric resins and semiconducting nanoparticles, providing insights into the synergistic effects of heterojunctions in photocatalytic systems. Future work could explore further optimization of the heterojunction structure, scalability of the synthesis, and long-term stability to move toward practical implementation in real-world settings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zhixiong Zheng: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Yazhou Zhou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Author contributions

Y.Z supervised this work. The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final

version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.apcata.2025.120353](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2025.120353).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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